

Economic Burden of the 2020 COVID-19 Hospitalizations in Spain

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Introduction

In Spain, the 2020 total health care expenditure surpassed €115 billion, covering 47.5 million people.¹ The health care burden increased due to additional financing required to address the COVID-19 pandemic. This study aimed to describe the direct costs of COVID-19 treatment of hospitalized patients during the first year of the pandemic.

+ Supplemental content

Author affiliations and article information are listed at the end of this article.

Methods

We conducted a nationwide, population-based retrospective economic evaluation of all COVID-19-related hospitalizations in Spanish hospitals in 2020. This study was approved by the CEIm Area de Salud Valladolid Este Ethics Review Board, which waived the informed consent requirement given the anonymous character of the data used in the study. We followed the [CHEERS](#) reporting guideline.

Data were collected from the Minimum Basic Data Set (MBDS), a clinical and administrative database that covers approximately 99.5% of public and private Spanish hospitals and includes discharge reports. Patients hospitalized for COVID-19 between January 1 and December 31, 2020, were selected. The MBDS excludes short-term admissions (<24 hours), emergency department care, and outpatient care. Patients with *International Statistical Classification of Diseases Tenth Revision, Clinical Modification* codes B97.29 and U07.1 as the primary diagnosis on admission were included in the analysis (eMethods in [Supplement 1](#)).

Hospital costs were calculated using diagnosis-related group data from the MBDS and were disaggregated by sex, age group, intensive care unit (ICU) admission, outcome (death or survival), and epidemic wave (first or second). All costs were expressed in euros in 2020 values. For discussion purposes, the European Central Bank currency equivalence in 2020 was used (eMethods in [Supplement 1](#)).

Results were reported as mean (95% CI) for continuous variables and frequency (percentage) for categorical variables. Differences between groups were assessed using an unpaired, 2-tailed *t* test; Mann-Whitney test; and Kruskal-Wallis test with Bonferroni correction adjustment for multiple comparisons ($\alpha = .05$) for continuous variables when appropriate. Statistical analysis was conducted with Python 3.9 (Python). Two-sided $P < .05$ indicated statistical significance.

Results

A total of 217 106 patients with a COVID-19 diagnosis (94 542 females [43.5%], 122 564 males [56.5%]; mean [SD] age, 67.1 [22.5] years) were admitted in 2020. Admission characteristics are described in [Table 1](#). The mean cost of admissions was €1 234 202 626.55 (total cost, €18 428 397 789.48), with a mean cost per patient of €5684.79 ([Table 2](#)) and €4880.76 for non-COVID-19 causes. The cost per wave was €623 077 956.36 in the first and €611 124 670.19 in the second, with no differences in mean cost per patient. To convert amounts to US dollars, multiply by 1.14.

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The ICU admissions accounted for 9.5% of all admissions, with a higher mean cost per patient than general admissions (€21 199.20 [95% CI, €20 908.84-€21489.56] vs €4122.96 [95% CI, €4109.15-€4136.77]; $P < .001$). Higher mean spending per patient was found in those who died vs survived (€8774.72 [95% CI, €8646.29-€8903.15] vs €5069.89 [95% CI, €5035.90- €5103.87]; $P < .001$) (Table 2). Males had a higher mean cost per patient than females (€6251.21 €6196.72- €6305.70] vs €4950.49 [95% CI, €4908.28-€4992.70]; $P < .001$). The highest mean cost per patient was among the 60- to 79-year group (Table 2).

Discussion

Expenditures for COVID-19-related hospitalizations in Spain amounted to €1.23 billion in 2020, which represented 6.7% of total hospital costs with a mean cost per patient that was 16% higher than for patients admitted for non-COVID-19 causes.¹ These costs were lower than those reported in studies

Table 1. Characteristics of Patients With COVID-19-Related Hospitalizations in 2020

Characteristic	No. (%) ^a
No. of patients	217 106
Sex	
Female	94 542 (43.5)
Male	122 564 (56.5)
Age, mean (95% CI), y	67.1 (67.03-67.18)
Length of stay, mean (95% CI), d	10.86 (10.81-10.91)
In-hospital death	36 034 (16.6)
Charlson Comorbidity Index, mean (95% CI)	1.35 (1.35-1.36)
ICU admission and intubation	
ICU admission	19 857 (9.2)
ICU death	6294 (2.9)
ICU length of stay, mean (95% CI)	15.7 (15.47-15.93)
Mechanical ventilation	14 527 (6.7)
Ventilatory assistance	12 303 (5.7)

Abbreviation: ICU, intensive care unit.

^a Values are expressed as absolute number (%) for categorical variables and as mean (95% CI) for continuous variables.

Table 2. Costs of COVID-19-Related Hospitalization

Description	Patients, No.	Total cost, € ^a	Mean cost per patient (95% CI), € ^a
All COVID-19 hospitalizations	217 106	1 234 202 626.55	5684.79 (5648.86-5720.73)
Epidemic wave			
First	109 018	623 077 956.36	5715.37 (5658.18-5772.55)
Second	108 088	611 124 670.19	5653.95 (5610.55-5697.35)
Type of admission			
General	197 249	813 250 043.85	4122.96 (4109.15-4136.77)
ICU	19 857	420 952 582.70	21 199.20 (20 908.84-21489.56)
Outcome			
Survival	181 072	918 014 423.38	5069.89 (5035.90-5103.87)
Death	36 034	316 188 203.17	8774.72 (8646.29-8903.15)
Sex			
Male	122 564	766 173 398.20	6251.21 (6196.72-6305.70)
Female	94 542	468 029 228.35	4950.49 (4908.28-4992.70)
Age group, y			
<40	14 156	61 674 501.59	4356.77 (4259.35-4454.20)
40-59	55 971	308 345 337.62	5509.02 (5436.25-5581.79)
60-79	85 437	588 135 960.84	6883.86 (6810.12-6957.59)
>79	61 542	276 046 826.50	4485.50 (4463.81-4507.19)

Abbreviation: ICU, intensive care unit.

^a To convert to US dollars, multiply by 1.14.

from Canada² (US \$12 728 for general and \$42 340 for ICU admission), Greece (\$10 110 and \$27 603.54, respectively),³ and the US (estimated mean cost, \$14 366).⁴ In contrast, costs were higher than those in Turkey (\$881.75 and \$2924, respectively)³ and Colombia⁵ (median cost, \$1688). These comparisons should be interpreted with caution due to different sample sizes and methods employed.

A study limitation was the use of MBDS, which estimates patient costs through diagnosis-related group, a world-renowned and consolidated American cost-estimation system.⁶ Results of this economic evaluation may be useful to health authorities for developing an economic strategy in preparation for future pandemics.

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Author Contributions: Drs Álvaro-Meca and Tamayo had full access to all of the data in the study and take responsibility for the integrity of the data and the accuracy of the data analysis. Drs Tamayo and Gutiérrez-Abejón were senior authors who contributed equally to this study.

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SUPPLEMENT 1.

eMethods.

SUPPLEMENT 2.

Data Sharing Statement

Supplementary Online Content

Álvarez-del Río B, Sánchez-de Prada L, Álvaro-Meca A, et al. Economic burden of the 2020 COVID-19 hospitalizations in Spain. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2023;6(1):e2250960. doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2022.50960

eMethods.

This supplementary material has been provided by the authors to give readers additional information about their work.

eMethods

Study design

A nationwide population-based retrospective study of all hospitalizations involving COVID-19 was carried out in Spanish hospitals (public and private) during the first year of the SARS-CoV2 pandemic, 2020.

Data were collected from the Minimum Basic Data Set (MBDS)¹ obtained by the National Surveillance System for Hospital Data in Spain and published by the Ministry of Health. The MBDS is a clinical and administrative data base fulfilled at the time of discharge with an estimated coverage of 99.5% of public and private Spanish hospitals. It provides encrypted information following the International Classification of Diseases 10th Revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-10-CM)² The data were treated with full confidentiality according to Spanish legislation. The study was approved by the Ethics Review Board (CEIm Area de Salud Valladolid Este, reference study PI 22-2855).

Measures

Hospitalized patients during 2020 were selected. The MBDS excludes programmed short-term admissions (less than 24 hours), emergency room and hospital outpatient care. COVID-19 patients with ICD-10-CM³ codes B97.29 and U07.1 as main diagnosis present on admission were selected.

Variables collected included age, sex, length of stay (LoS), in-hospital death, admission in intensive care unit (ICU), ICU length of stay, ICU death, mechanical ventilation and ventilatory assistance. Charlson comorbidities index was computed using ICD-10 coding algorithms developed by Quan et al.³ During 2020, SARS-CoV2 circulated in two waves in Spain, the first one since its emergence until June 30th, 2020, and the second from July 1st, 2020, until December 31st, 2020.⁴

COVID-19 related hospital costs were calculated using diagnosis-related groups (DRG) data extracted from the MBDS.¹ These costs were disaggregated based on sex, age groups (<40, 40-59, 60-79, >79 years old), ICU-admission, outcome (death/alive) and epidemiological waves (first and second). All costs were expressed in euros (€) in 2020 values. For discussion purposes the annual currency equivalence in 2020 was 1€ = 1.1422\$ United States dollars (USD)⁵

Statistical analysis

Results were reported as mean (95% confidence interval) for continuous variables and as frequencies and percentages for categorical variables. Differences between groups were assessed using an unpaired, 2-tailed t test; Mann-Whitney test; and Kruskal-Wallis test with Bonferroni correction adjustment for multiple comparisons ($\alpha = 0.05$) for continuous variables when appropriate. Statistical analysis was conducted with Python 3.9 (Python). (Two-sided $P < .05$ indicated statistical significance).

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Data Sharing Statement

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Data

Data available: No

Additional Information

Explanation for why data not available: The MDDBS is the property of the Ministry of Health. Therefore, any researcher can request the data related to this article from the Ministry of Health by email (icmbd@msssi.es), by fax (+34915964111), or by mail (Instituto de Información Sanitaria, Área de Información y Estadísticas Asistenciales, Ministerio de Sanidad, Consumo y Bienestar Social. Paseo del Prado 18-20; 28071 Madrid. Spain).